

Hermite Polynomials

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Index

1	Hermite's differential equation	2
2	Hermite polynomials	5
3	Hermite's functions of the second kind.....	11
4	Examples and applications	11
5	Quantistic harmonic oscillations	14
6	References.....	19

1 Hermite's differential equation

DEF. 1 (Hermite's equation). It is the following linear ordinary differential equation of the second order:

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad y'' - 2xy' + 2ny = 0$$

where n is a real number.

PROP. 1 (*general integral*). It can be shown that the general integral of the Hermite's equation is the sum of a finite polynomial given by

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad H_n(x) = A_n \sum_{k=0}^{E(\frac{n}{2})} \frac{(-1)^{2k}}{k!(n-2k)!} (2x)^{n-2k}, \quad \begin{aligned} E\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) &= \frac{n}{2}, & A_n &= c_0(-1)^{\frac{n}{2}} \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)! & \text{even } n \\ E\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) &= \frac{n-1}{2}, & A_n &= \frac{c_1}{2}(-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! & \text{odd } n \end{aligned}$$

and an infinite polynomial, given by

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \begin{cases} h_n(x) = c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{(n-1)(n-3)\dots(n-2h+1)}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} & \text{even } n \\ h_n(x) = c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{n(n-2)(n-4)\dots(n-2h+2)}{(2h)!} x^{2h} & \text{odd } n \end{cases}$$

where c_0, c_1 are arbitrary constants.

Proof. We search the solution in the form of the power series $y = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k x^{k+\beta}$ with $c_k = 0$ for $k < 0$ (Frobenius's method). The derivatives of such a function are:

$$y' = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k (k + \beta) x^{k+\beta-1}, \quad y'' = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k (k + \beta)(k + \beta - 1) x^{k+\beta-2}$$

Substituting y, y' and y'' in Eq. 1 we have

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k (k + \beta)(k + \beta - 1) x^{k+\beta-2} - 2 \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k (k + \beta) x^{k+\beta} + 2n \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k x^{k+\beta} = 0$$

We set now $h = k - 2$ in the first sum and we have

$$\sum_{h=-\infty}^{\infty} c_{h+2} (h + 2 + \beta)(h + \beta + 1) x^{h+\beta} - 2 \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k (k + \beta) x^{k+\beta} + 2n \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k x^{k+\beta} = 0$$

With abuse of notation we now use again k as index in the first sum, and we have:

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} [c_{k+2} (k + \beta + 2)(k + \beta + 1) - 2c_k (k + \beta - n)] x^{k+\beta} = 0$$

This must be true for any $x \in \mathbb{R}$, therefore it must be

$$c_{k+2}(k + \beta + 2)(k + \beta + 1) - 2c_k(k + \beta - n) = 0 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad c_{k+2}(k + \beta + 2)(k + \beta + 1) = 2c_k(k + \beta - n), \quad \forall k \geq 0$$

It must be true for any k , therefore it is true in particular for $k = -2$ and this means that it must be $c_0\beta(\beta - 1) = 2c_{-2}(\beta - n - 2)$. Since $c_{-2} = 0$, either $\beta = 0$ or $\beta = 1$. Let us consider the case $\beta = 0$. Then, we have

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad c_{k+2} = 2 \frac{k-n}{(k+2)(k+1)} c_k, \quad \forall k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Let us see how these coefficients behave when we express them as a function of c_0, c_1 :

$$k = 0 \rightarrow c_2 = -\frac{2n}{2!} c_0, \quad k = 1 \rightarrow c_3 = -2 \frac{n-1}{3 \cdot 2} c_1$$

$$k = 2 \rightarrow c_4 = -2 \frac{n-2}{4 \cdot 3} c_2 = (-1)^2 2^2 \frac{n(n-2)}{4!} c_0$$

$$k = 3 \rightarrow c_5 = 2 \frac{3-n}{5 \cdot 4} c_3 = (-1)^2 2^2 \frac{(n-1)(n-3)}{5!} c_1$$

$$k = 4 \rightarrow c_6 = -2 \frac{n-4}{6 \cdot 5} c_4 = (-1)^3 2^3 \frac{n(n-2)(n-4)}{6!} c_0$$

$$k = 5 \rightarrow c_7 = -2 \frac{n-5}{7 \cdot 6} c_5 = (-1)^3 2^3 \frac{(n-1)(n-3)(n-5)}{7!} c_1$$

$$k = 6 \rightarrow c_8 = -2 \frac{n-6}{8 \cdot 7} c_6 = (-1)^4 2^4 \frac{n(n-2)(n-4)(n-6)}{8!} c_0$$

$$k = 7 \rightarrow c_9 = -2 \frac{n-7}{9 \cdot 8} c_7 = (-1)^4 2^4 \frac{(n-1)(n-3)(n-5)(n-7)}{9!} c_1$$

These expressions suggest the formulae:

$$\begin{cases} k = 2h - 2, & c_{2h} = (-1)^h 2^h \frac{n(n-2)(n-4) \dots (n-2h+2)}{(2h)!} c_0 \\ k = 2h - 1, & c_{2h+1} = (-1)^h 2^h \frac{(n-1)(n-3) \dots (n-5)(n-2h+1)}{(2h+1)!} c_1 \end{cases}, \quad h = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Therefore, the solution of the differential equation is

$$y_n(x) = c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^h 2^h n(n-2) \dots (n-2h+2) x^{2h}}{(2h)!} + c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^h 2^h (n-1) \dots (n-2h+1) x^{2h+1}}{(2h+1)!}$$

We note that for even n the first sum is finite, while for odd n it is the second one to be finite. More specifically, if we focus on the finite sums only, we have

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad \begin{cases} y_n(x) = c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\frac{n}{2}} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{n(n-2)(n-4)\dots(n-2h+2)}{(2h)!} x^{2h} & \text{even } n \\ y_n(x) = c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\frac{n-1}{2}} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{(n-1)(n-3)\dots(n-2h+1)}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} & \text{odd } n \end{cases}$$

If we focus only on infinite sums we have

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad \begin{cases} y_n(x) = c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{(n-1)(n-3)\dots(n-2h+1)}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} & \text{even } n \\ y_n(x) = c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{n(n-2)(n-4)\dots(n-2h+2)}{(2h)!} x^{2h} & \text{odd } n \end{cases}$$

Now we focus on Eq. 6 and we search for a compact expression. We note that for n even we have

$$n(n-2)(n-4)\dots(n-2h+2) = 2^h \frac{n}{2} \left(\frac{n}{2}-1\right) \left(\frac{n}{2}-2\right) \dots \left(\frac{n}{2}-h+1\right) = 2^h \frac{\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)!}{\left(\frac{n}{2}-h\right)!}$$

while for odd n we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (n-1)(n-3)(n-5)\dots(n-2h+1) = \\ & = 2^h \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right) \left(\frac{n-1}{2}-1\right) \left(\frac{n-1}{2}-2\right) \dots \left(\frac{n-1}{2}-h+1\right) = 2^{h-1} \frac{\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)!}{\left(\frac{n-1}{2}-h\right)!} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we have found that Eq. 6 can be written as

$$\begin{cases} y_n(x) = c_0 \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)! \sum_{h=0}^{\frac{n}{2}} \frac{(-1)^h 2^{2h}}{(2h)! \left(\frac{n}{2}-h\right)!} x^{2h} & \text{even } n \\ y_n(x) = c_1 \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \sum_{h=0}^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \frac{(-1)^h 2^{2h}}{(2h+1)! \left(\frac{n-1}{2}-h\right)!} x^{2h+1} & \text{odd } n \end{cases} \Rightarrow$$

$$\begin{cases} y_n(x) = c_0 \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)! \sum_{h=0}^{\frac{n}{2}} \frac{(-1)^h}{\left(\frac{n}{2}-h\right)! (2h)!} (2x)^{2h} & \text{even } n \\ y_n(x) = \frac{c_1}{2} \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \sum_{h=0}^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \frac{(-1)^h}{\left(\frac{n-1}{2}-h\right)! (2h+1)!} (2x)^{2h+1} & \text{odd } n \end{cases}$$

Is it possible to write these two sums with a single formula? Yes, it is and the trick is to put the addends in the reverse order. For even n we have

$$y_n(x) = c_0 \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)! \left(\frac{1}{\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)! 0!} + \frac{(-1)}{\left(\frac{n}{2}-1\right)! 2!} 2^2 x^2 + \frac{(-1)^2}{\left(\frac{n}{2}-2\right)! 4!} 2^4 x^4 + \dots + \frac{(-1)^{\frac{n}{2}-3}}{3! (n-6)!} (2x)^{n-6} + \right. \\ \left. + \frac{(-1)^{\frac{n}{2}-2}}{2! (n-4)!} (2x)^{n-4} + \frac{(-1)^{\frac{n}{2}-1}}{1! (n-2)!} (2x)^{n-2} + \frac{(-1)^{\frac{n}{2}}}{0! n!} (2x)^n \right)$$

Now we consider the addends in the reverse order and we have

$$y_n(x) = c_0 (-1)^{\frac{n}{2}} \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)! \left(\frac{(2x)^n}{0! n!} + \frac{(-1)^1}{1! (n-2)!} (2x)^{n-2} + \frac{(-1)^2}{2! (n-4)!} (2x)^{n-4} + \dots \right) \Rightarrow \\ y_n(x) = c_0 (-1)^{\frac{n}{2}} \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)! \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{n}{2}} \frac{(-1)^{2k}}{k! (n-2k)!} (2x)^{n-2k}, \quad n \text{ even}$$

With the same approach the reader can prove that

$$y_n(x) = \frac{c_1}{2} (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \frac{(-1)^{2k}}{k! (n-2k)!} (2x)^{n-2k}, \quad n \text{ odd}$$

This proves Eq. 2, where we have indicated the polynomial $y_n(x)$ as $H_n(x)$ (the reason for this choice will be clear in a moment). And the proof is concluded ■

2 Hermite polynomials

DEF. 2 (Hermite polynomials). The polynomials in Eq. 2 with $A_n = n!$ are called Hermite polynomials. This means that we assume

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad c_0 = (-1)^{\frac{n}{2}} \frac{n!}{\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)!}, \quad c_1 = (-1)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} 2 \frac{n!}{\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)!}$$

This means that Hermite polynomials can be written

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad H_n(x) = n! \sum_{k=0}^{E\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)} \frac{(-1)^{2k}}{k! (n-2k)!} (2x)^{n-2k}, \quad E\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) = \frac{n}{2}, \quad \text{even } n \\ E\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) = \frac{n-1}{2}, \quad \text{odd } n$$

PROP. 2 (general integral). The general integral of the Hermite equation can be written

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad y_n(x) = C_1 H_n(x) + C_2 H_n(x) \int \frac{e^{x^2}}{H_n^2(x)} dx$$

Proof. We search for solutions in the form $y_n(x) = g(x)H_n(x)$. Since

$$y_n'(x) = g'(x)H_n(x) + g(x)H_n'(x)$$

$$y_n''(x) = g''(x)H_n(x) + 2g'(x)H_n'(x) + g(x)H_n''(x)$$

by substituting $y_n(x), y_n'(x), y_n''(x)$ in Eq. 1 we have

$$\begin{aligned} g''(x)H_n(x) + 2g'(x)H_n'(x) + g(x)H_n''(x) - 2x(g'(x)H_n(x) + g(x)H_n'(x)) + 2ng(x)H_n(x) &= 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow g''(x)H_n(x) + 2g'(x)(H_n'(x) - xH_n(x)) + g(x)(H_n''(x) - 2xH_n'(x) + 2nH_n(x)) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

We recognize that $H_n''(x) - 2xH_n'(x) + 2nH_n(x) = 0$, therefore we have found:

$$g''(x)H_n(x) + 2g'(x)(H_n'(x) - xH_n(x)) = 0$$

We now introduce the function $f(x) = g'(x)$, and we have

$$\frac{f'(x)}{f(x)} = -2 \frac{H_n'(x) - xH_n(x)}{H_n(x)}$$

If we integrate both hands of the equation we have

$$\ln f(x) = -2 \ln H_n(x) + x^2 \Rightarrow f(x) = \frac{e^{x^2}}{H_n^2(x)} \Rightarrow g(x) = \int \frac{e^{x^2}}{H_n^2(x)} dx$$

Since $f(x) = g'(x)$, by integrating both hands of the equation we obtain what we wanted to prove ■

PROP. 3 (*Rodrigues' formula*). It is possible to prove that

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad H_n(x) = (-1)^n e^{x^2} \frac{d^n(e^{-x^2})}{dx^n}$$

Proof. First, we recognize that $(-1)^n e^{x^2} \frac{d^n(e^{-x^2})}{dx^n}$ is a polynomial of order n whose highest term is $(-1)^n (-2x)^n = (2x)^n$. This means that if we show that it is a solution of the Hermite equation, it must be the Hermite polynomial. We now make the position $u_n(x) = e^{-x^2}$ and we have $u_n'(x) + 2xu_n(x) = 0$. By differentiating this equation $n + 1$ times we have

$$\begin{aligned} u_n^{(n+2)}(x) + 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n+1} \binom{n+1}{k} x^{(n+1-k)} u_n^{(k)}(x) &= \\ = u_n^{(n+2)}(x) + 2 \left(\binom{n+1}{n} x^{(1)} u_n^{(n)}(x) + \binom{n+1}{n+1} x^{(0)} u_n^{(n+1)}(x) \right) &\Rightarrow \\ u_n^{(n+2)}(x) + 2x u_n^{(n+1)}(x) + 2(n+1) u_n^{(n)}(x) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Let us now define the function $v = (-1)^n u^{(n)}$ and we have

$$v'' + 2xv' + 2(n+1)v = 0$$

Now we define the function $y = e^{x^2}v$ (so that $v = ye^{-x^2}$) and we have $v' = (y' - 2xy)e^{-x^2}$ and $v^{(2)} = (y^{(2)} - 4xy' + 2y(2x^2 - 1))e^{-x^2}$. Therefore, we have found

$$(y'' - 4xy' + 2y(2x^2 - 1))e^{-x^2} + 2x(y' - 2xy)e^{-x^2} + 2(n + 1)ye^{-x^2} = 0$$

And with some manipulation we find $y'' - 4xy' + 4yx^2 + 2xy' - 4yx^2 + 2ny = 0$, which can be simplified in $y'' - 2xy' + 2ny = 0$. This means that

$$y = e^{x^2}v = (-1)^n e^{x^2} u^{(n)} = (-1)^n e^{x^2} \frac{d^n(e^{-x^2})}{dx^n}$$

is a solution of the Hermite equation, and this means that y is in fact H_n ■

PROP. 4 (*generating function*). It is possible to prove that

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad e^{2tx-t^2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H_n(x)}{n!} t^n$$

Proof. Using Rodrigues' formula we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H_n(x)}{n!} t^n = e^{x^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{d^n(e^{-x^2})}{dx^n} \frac{t^n}{n!}$$

If we now consider the Taylor's expansion of function f with center x and increment $-t$ we have

$$f(x-t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{d^n f}{dx^n} \frac{t^n}{n!}$$

Let's now consider in particular function $f(x) = e^{-x^2}$:

$$e^{-(x-t)^2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{d^n(e^{-x^2})}{dx^n} \frac{t^n}{n!}$$

By comparison, we have proved that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H_n(x)}{n!} t^n = e^{x^2} e^{-(x-t)^2} = e^{x^2} e^{-(x^2+t^2-2xt)} = e^{-(t^2-2xt)}$$

which agrees with Eq. 11 ■

Example 1 (*a few polynomials*). An interesting way to calculate the Hermite polynomials is to use the generating function. Since we know that $e^x = 1 + x + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots$, we can also write

$$\begin{aligned} e^{2tx-t^2} &= 1 + 2tx - t^2 + \frac{(2tx - t^2)^2}{2} + \frac{(2tx - t^2)^3}{3!} + \dots = \\ &= 1 + 2tx - t^2 + \frac{(2x - t)^2 t^2}{2} + \frac{(2x - t)^3 t^3}{3!} + \dots = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 1 + 2tx - t^2 + \frac{(4x^2 + t^2 - 4xt)t^2}{2} + \frac{(8x^3 - 8x^2t + 4xt - t^3)t^3}{3!} + \dots = \\
&= 1 + 2tx - t^2 + \frac{4x^2t^2 + t^4 - 4xt^3}{2} + \frac{8x^3t^3 - 8x^2t^4 + 4xt^4 - t^6}{3!} + \dots
\end{aligned}$$

Now we collect with respect to powers of t and we have:

$$e^{2tx-t^2} = 1 + 2tx + (4x^2 - 2)\frac{t^2}{2!} + (8x^3 - 12x)\frac{t^3}{3!} + \dots = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H_n(x)}{n!} t^n$$

Therefore, we have found

$$H_0(x) = 1, \quad H_1(x) = 2x, \quad H_2(x) = 4x^2 - 2, \quad H_3(x) = 8x^3 - 12x$$

Another approach to calculating these polynomials is to directly use Rodrigues' formula.

Figure 1. First five Hermite polynomials, generated by the recurrence relation (Eq. 14) by CODE 1.

PROP. 5 (derivative). It is possible to prove that

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad H'_n(x) = 2nH_{n-1}(x)$$

Proof. By derivation with respect to x of the generating function we find $2te^{2tx-t^2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H'_n(x)}{n!} t^n$ and by substitution of the generating function itself in this expression we have

$$2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H_n(x)}{n!} t^{n+1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H'_n(x)}{n!} t^n$$

This means that it must be true that $2 \frac{H_{n-1}(x)}{(n-1)!} t^n = \frac{H'_n(x)}{n!} t^n$ or, in other words, $H'_n(x) = n! 2 \frac{H_{n-1}(x)}{(n-1)!}$ which, after simplification of the factorials, is exactly what we wanted to prove ■

PROP. 6 (*recursion formula*). It is possible to prove that

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad H_{n+1}(x) = 2xH_n(x) - 2nH_{n-1}(x)$$

By derivation of Rodrigues' formula we find

$$H'_n(x) = (-1)^n \left(2xe^{x^2} \frac{d^n(e^{-x^2})}{dx^n} + e^{x^2} \frac{d^{n+1}(e^{-x^2})}{dx^{n+1}} \right) = 2xH_n(x) + H_{n+1}(x)$$

But we have calculated an expression for the derivative of the Hermite function (Eq. 13) and we find $2nH_{n-1}(x) = 2xH_n(x) + H_{n+1}(x)$, which is what we wanted to prove ■

CODE 1 (plotting). We can use the recurrence formula to calculate and plot the first Hermite polynomials knowing that $H_0 = 1, H_1 = 2x$. The script is straightforward (see below) and it generates

```
# file name: Recursive_Hermite_Poly.py
#
# This script derives the values of the first n (specified by the user)
# Hermite polynomials and plot them within an interval specified by the user
#
import os # functions for interacting with the operating system
import pandas as pd # dataframes similar to R
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt # a plotting library
import math # mathematical functions
import numpy as np # arrays and matrices
#
# Change the drectory, to the folder of the script
#
script_dir = os.path.dirname(os.path.abspath(__file__))
print(f"script_dir: {script_dir}")
os.chdir(script_dir)
#
# Number of Hermite Polynomials to calculate, and number of values of x
#
N = 5 # first n+1 Hermite Polynomials (n>1)
r = 100 # number of values for x in interval
a = -1 # left extreme of the interval
b = 1 # right extreme of the interval
x = np.linspace(a, b, r) # x values
#
# Hermite Polynomials are stored in a data frame such that column n is P_n(x)
#
mydata = pd.DataFrame(0.0, index=range(r), columns=range(N))
#
# Store H_0 and H_1, 1 and 2x respectively. Store also the abscissa
#
for i in range(r):
    mydata.at[i,0] = 1.0 # H_0(x) = 1
mydata[1] = 2*x # H_1(x)
#
```

```

# Calculate values from H_2 to H_n using the recurrence relation
#
for n in range(1,N-1):
    print(f"Calculating H_{n+1}(x)")
    for i in range(r):
        H1 = mydata.at[i,n-1] # P_{(n-1)}(x)
        H2 = mydata.at[i,n] # P_{(n)}(x)
        H3 = 2*x[i]*H2 - 2*n*H1 # H_{(n+1)}(x)
        mydata.at[i,n+1] = H3 # store H_{(n+1)}(x)
#
# Plot
#
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))
for n in range(0,N):
    Hn = mydata[n]
    plt.plot(x, Hn, label=f'$H_{n}(x)$')
plt.xlabel('abscissa (x)')
plt.ylabel('$H_n(x)$')
plt.title('Hermite Polynomials $H_n(x)$')
plt.legend()
plt.grid(True)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('Hermite_Polynomials.jpg', dpi=300)
plt.close() # Close the current figure

```

PROP. 7 (*orthogonality*). Hermite polynomials are mutually orthogonal. More precisely, we have

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_m(x) H_n(x) dx = \begin{cases} 0 & m \neq n \\ 2^n n! \sqrt{\pi} & m = n \end{cases}$$

Proof. By using the generating function we can write

$$e^{2xt-t^2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{H_n(x)}{n!} t^n, \quad e^{2xs-s^2} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{H_m(x)}{m!} s^m$$

Therefore, we have

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} e^{2xt-t^2} e^{2xs-s^2} dx = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} \frac{H_n(x) H_m(x)}{n! m!} t^n s^m dx$$

We now work on the exponent of the argument for the integral of the left hand:

$$\begin{aligned} 2xt - t^2 + 2xs - s^2 - x^2 &= -(x^2 - 2xt - 2xs + t^2 + s^2 + 2st - 2st) = \\ &= -(x^2 - 2(t+s)x + (t+s)^2 - 2st) = -((x+t+s)^2 - 2st) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the left-hand integral becomes

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-((x+t+s)^2 - 2st)} dx = e^{2st} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-(x+t+s)^2} dx = e^{2st} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-u^2} du$$

We recognize the error function $\text{erf}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_{-x}^x e^{-x^2} dx$. Since $\text{erf}(\infty) = 1$, we have

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-((x+t+s)^2-2st)} dx = e^{2st}\sqrt{\pi}$$

Therefore, by substituting in Eq. 16, we have

$$e^{2st}\sqrt{\pi} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} \frac{H_n(x)H_m(x)}{n! m!} t^n s^m dx$$

By series expansion of the first term we have

$$\sqrt{\pi} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{2^k s^k t^k}{k!} = \frac{t^n s^m}{n! m!} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_n(x)H_m(x) dx$$

We recognize that only addends with $n = m$ are represented on the left hand side, therefore we have found

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_n(x)H_m(x) dx = 0, \quad n \neq m$$

When $n = m$ we have

$$\sqrt{\pi} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{2^k s^k t^k}{k!} = \frac{t^k s^k}{k! k!} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_k(x)H_k(x) dx$$

By comparisons of the terms of the same degree we have $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_k(x)H_k(x) dx = k! 2^k \sqrt{\pi}$ and we have proved this theorem ■

3 Hermite's functions of the second kind

DEF. 3 (Hermite's function of the second kind). The infinite series in Eq. 3 are called Hermite's functions of the second kind.

PROP. 8. It is possible to show that $h_n(x) \propto H_n(x) \int \frac{e^{x^2}}{H_n^2(x)} dx$.

Proof. This is immediately verified by comparison of the general integral of Eq. 10 with the general integral expressed as $y_n(x) = C_1 H_n(x) + C_2 h_n(x)$ ■

4 Examples and applications

PROP. 9 (*series expansion*). If $f(x)$ and its derivative have a finite number of discontinuities in \mathbb{R} , then wherever they are continuous functions, we have

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad \begin{cases} f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k H_k(x) \\ A_k = \frac{1}{2^k k! \sqrt{\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} f(x) H_k(x) dx \end{cases}$$

while in the points of discontinuity, we have $\frac{f(x-0)+f(x+0)}{2} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k H_k(x)$.

Proof. We derive here the expression of the generalised Fourier coefficients A_k assuming that the expansion holds:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k H_k(x) \Rightarrow \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} f(x) H_m(x) dx = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_k(x) H_m(x) dx = A_m \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_m^2(x) dx \end{aligned}$$

Since $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_m^2(x) dx = 2^n m! \sqrt{\pi}$ (Eq. 17), we find $A_m = \frac{1}{2^n m! \sqrt{\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) H_m(x) dx$ ■

Example 2 (*series expansion*). We now see an example of series expansion in Hermite polynomials. Let's consider the function $f(x) = x^3$. We have:

$$x^3 = A_0 + A_1 2x + A_2 2(2x^2 - 1) + A_3 2(4x^3 - 6x) + \dots$$

It must be $A_0 = A_2 = 0$ and also $A_k = 0$ for $k \geq 4$. Therefore, we have

$$x^3 = A_1 2x + A_3 2(4x^3 - 6x) = (2A_1 - 12A_3)x + 8A_3 x^3$$

This means that $A_1 = 6A_3$ and $A_3 = \frac{1}{8}$. So we have found $A_1 = 6A_3 = \frac{6}{8} = \frac{3}{4}$ and the expansion is:

$$x^3 = \frac{3}{4} H_1(x) + \frac{1}{8} H_3(x)$$

Example 3 (*one integral*). To calculate the integral $I_n = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2 e^{-x^2} H_n(x) dx$ we observe that

$$x^2 = \frac{4x^2 - 2 + 2}{4} = \frac{4x^2 - 2}{4} + \frac{1}{2} = \frac{H_2(x)}{4} + \frac{H_0(x)}{2}$$

Then, the integral becomes

$$I_n = \frac{1}{4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_2(x) H_n(x) dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_0(x) H_n(x) dx$$

According to PROP. 7 we can now write

$$I_0 = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_0(x) H_0(x) dx = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}, \quad I_2 = \frac{1}{4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} H_2(x) H_2(x) dx = \frac{1}{4} 2^2 2! \sqrt{\pi} = 2\sqrt{\pi}$$

Example 4 (*general integral for $n = 0$*). In this example, we derive the expression of the general integral of Eq. 1 for $n = 0$. From Eq. 10 we have

$$y_0(x) = C_1 H_0(x) + C_2 H_0(x) \int \frac{e^{x^2}}{H_0^2(x)} dx = C_1 + C_2 \int_0^x e^{\xi^2} d\xi = C_1 + C_2 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \int_0^x \frac{\xi^{2h}}{h!} d\xi \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad y_0(x) = C_1 + C_2 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2h+1}}{h!(2h+1)}$$

If we use the expression of the Hermite's functions of the second kind (Eq. 3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} h_0(x) &= c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{(-1)(-3) \dots (-2h+1)}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} = \\ &= c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{2^h (2h-1)(2h-3) \dots 3 \cdot 1}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} = c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{2^h (2h-1)!!}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} \end{aligned}$$

We note now that

$$\begin{aligned} (2h+1)! &= (2h+1)2h(2h-1)(2h-2) \dots 2 \cdot 1 = \\ &= (2h+1)(2h)! = (2h+1)(2h)!!(2h-1)!! = 2^h(2h+1)h!(2h-1)!! \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, we have

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad h_0(x) = c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2h+1}}{h!(2h+1)}$$

and we find again the general integral of Eq. 18.

Example 5 (*general integral for $n = 1$*). If we use the expression of the Hermite's functions of the second kind (Eq. 3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} h_1(x) &= c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{(1-2)(1-4) \dots (1-2h+2)}{(2h)!} x^{2h} = \\ &= c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} 2^h \frac{1 \cdot 3 \dots (2h-3)}{(2h)!} x^{2h} = c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{2^h (2h-3)!!}{(2h)!} x^{2h} \end{aligned}$$

Since $\frac{2^h(2h-3)!!}{(2h)!} = \frac{2^h(2h-3)!!}{(2h)!!(2h-1)!!} = \frac{2^h}{(2h)!!(2h-1)} = \frac{2^h}{2^h h!(2h-1)} = \frac{1}{h!(2h-1)}$, we have

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad h_1(x) = c_0 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2h}}{h!(2h-1)}$$

We conclude that the general integral in this case is

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad y_1(x) = C_1 x + C_2 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2h}}{h!(2h-1)}$$

If we use Eq. 10 instead, we have

$$y_1(x) = C_1 H_1(x) + C_2 H_1(x) \int \frac{e^{x^2}}{H_1^2(x)} dx = C_1 x + C_2 x \int_0^x \xi^{-1} e^{\xi^2} d\xi$$

Now, since

$$\int_0^x \xi^{-1} e^{\xi^2} d\xi = \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \int_0^x \frac{\xi^{2h-2}}{h!} d\xi = \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2h-1}}{h! (2h-1)}$$

we have found again the same expression in Eq. 21.

Example 6 (*general integral for $n = 2$*). If we use the expression of the Hermite's functions of the second kind (Eq. 3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} h_2(x) &= c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (-1)^h 2^h \frac{(2-1)(2-3) \dots (2-2h+1)}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} = \\ &= c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} 2^h \frac{-1 \cdot 1 \cdot 3 \dots (2h-3)}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} = -c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} 2^h \frac{(2h-3)!!}{(2h+1)!} x^{2h+1} \end{aligned}$$

Since $\frac{2^h(2h-3)!!}{(2h+1)!} = \frac{2^h(2h-3)!!}{(2h+1)!!(2h)!!} = \frac{1}{(2h+1)(2h-1)h!}$, we have

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad h_2(x) = -c_1 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2h+1}}{(2h+1)(2h-1)h!}$$

Therefore, the general integral is

$$\text{Eq. 23} \quad y_2(x) = C_1(2x^2 - 1) + C_2 \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2h+1}}{(2h+1)(2h-1)h!}$$

5 Quantistic harmonic oscillations

Example 7 (*linear harmonic oscillator*). Schrödinger's equation for a particle in stationary cases is written as:

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2} + \frac{8\pi^2 m}{h^2} (E - U) \psi = 0$$

where $\psi(x, y, z)$ is the famous wave function of the particle, $|\psi(x, y, z)|^2$ is the probability of finding its mass at position (x, y, z) , m is its mass, E is its total energy and $U(x, y, z)$ is the potential energy. Also, $h = 6.625 \cdot 10^{-34} J \cdot s$ is Planck's constant. If we consider a linear harmonic oscillator on axis x , the potential energy due to the attractive force of a spring with a constant k is

$$\frac{dU}{dx} = -(-kx) = kx \Rightarrow U = \frac{k}{2} x^2$$

and the equation becomes

$$\text{Eq. 25} \quad \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{8\pi^2 m}{h^2} \left(E - \frac{k}{2} x^2 \right) \psi = 0, \quad \begin{cases} m\omega^2 = k & m\omega = \sqrt{km} \\ \omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} & \hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi} \end{cases}$$

We now consider the substitution $\xi = x \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}}$ and we have

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}} = \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}$$

Substitution in the above equation gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{2\pi m \omega}{h} + \frac{8\pi^2 m}{h^2} \left(E - \frac{m\omega^2}{2} \frac{h}{2\pi m \omega} \xi^2 \right) \psi &= 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{2\pi m \omega}{h} + \frac{2\pi m \omega}{h} \left(\frac{4\pi}{h\omega} E - 4\pi \frac{m\omega^2}{2} \frac{1}{2\pi m \omega^2} \xi^2 \right) \psi &= 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{2\pi m \omega}{h} + \frac{2\pi m \omega}{h} \left(\frac{4\pi}{h\omega} E - \xi^2 \right) \psi &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

We conclude with the nondimensional version of Eq. 25:

$$\text{Eq. 26} \quad \frac{d^2 \psi}{d\xi^2} + (\epsilon - \xi^2) \psi = 0, \quad \begin{cases} \epsilon = \frac{4\pi E}{h} \sqrt{\frac{m}{k}} \\ \xi = x \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}} \end{cases}$$

We now show that this nondimensional version of the Schrödinger's equation can be transformed into the Hermite differential equation by considering the substitution

$$\text{Eq. 27} \quad \psi(\xi) = y(\xi) e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{2}}$$

By derivation with respect to ξ we have

$$\frac{d\psi}{d\xi} = (y' - y\xi) e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{2}}, \quad \frac{d^2 \psi}{d\xi^2} = (y'' - 2\xi y' + (\xi^2 - 1)y) e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{2}}$$

Therefore, the equation becomes

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad y'' - 2\xi y' + (\epsilon - 1)y = 0$$

The solutions of Hermite equation for n non integer are only the Hermite functions of the second kind. These functions are unlimited though (we won't touch the convergence of h_n here), therefore the only meaningful solutions of Eq. 28 are the solutions for n integer, and in particular the Hermite polynomials. This means that it must be $\epsilon - 1 = 2n$ integer, which means

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad E = \frac{h}{4\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} (2n + 1), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

The solutions are $\psi(\xi) = CH_n(\xi) e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{2}}$ which, in the original reference system, can be written

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad \psi(x) = C H_n \left(x \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}} \right) e^{-\frac{\pi m \omega}{h} x^2}$$

with C an arbitrary constant. We can derive this constant by asking that the probability of finding the particle on the entire x axis must be one:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi^2(x) dx = C^2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_n^2 \left(x \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}} \right) e^{-2\frac{\pi m \omega}{h} x^2} dx = 1$$

We note now that the integral can be written

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_n^2 \left(x \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}} \right) e^{-2\frac{\pi m \omega}{h} x^2} dx = \sqrt{\frac{h}{2\pi m \omega}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_n^2(\xi) e^{-\xi^2} d\xi = 2^n n! \sqrt{\frac{h}{2m\omega}}$$

where we have used PROP. 7. Therefore, we have $C^2 2^n n! \sqrt{\frac{h}{2m\omega}} = 1 \Rightarrow C^2 = \frac{1}{2^n n!} \sqrt{\frac{2m\omega}{h}}$ and the conclusion is that the wave function of the harmonic oscillator is

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad \psi(x) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2^n n!} \sqrt{\frac{2m\omega}{h}}} H_n \left(x \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m \omega}{h}} \right) e^{-\frac{\pi m \omega}{h} x^2}, \quad E = \frac{h}{4\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} (2n + 1), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

We can use the corresponding classical harmonic oscillator to get an estimation of the amplitude of the oscillations and also to perform a comparison between the wave function in quantum theory and wave function in the corresponding system in classic mechanics. We have that the kinetic energy at the two extremes of the oscillation ($x = \pm A$) must be zero, so we have

$$\frac{k}{2} A^2 = E \Rightarrow A = \sqrt{\frac{2}{k} E} = \sqrt{(2n + 1) \frac{\omega h}{2k\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{2n + 1}{2m\omega\pi}} h \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 32} \quad A = \sqrt{\frac{2n+1}{2m\omega\pi}} h = \sqrt{\frac{2n+1}{m\omega}} \hbar$$

The position of the corresponding classical harmonic oscillator is $x(t) = A \cos(\omega t + \phi)$ where the phase ϕ depends on the initial condition. To derive the associated wave function we use the harmonic stochastic process [4] and we have

$$\text{Eq. 33} \quad f_X(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq -A \\ \frac{1}{\pi\sqrt{A^2 - x^2}} & -A < x < A \\ 0 & x \geq A \end{cases}$$

Example 8 (*hydrogen molecule*). The quantistic harmonic oscillator is used as a model for diatomic molecules. It can be shown that a system of two masses m_1, m_2 connected by a spring can be studied a single mass

$$\mu = \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_1 + m_2}, \quad \left(\omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{\mu}}, \quad A = \sqrt{\frac{2n+1}{2\mu\omega\pi}} h \right)$$

(called reduced mass) connected by the same spring to a restraint connected to the reference system. If we consider, in particular a diatomic molecule where both atoms are the same, we have $\mu = m/2$. In particular, in the case of the H_2 molecule we have $\mu = \frac{m}{2}$ with $m = 1.673 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ kg}$. To derive the elastic constant we use the experimental value of the vibrational wave number ν which is given by the ratio between the frequency of the system and the speed of light:

$$\nu = \frac{1}{Tc} = \frac{\omega}{2\pi c} = \frac{\sqrt{k/\mu}}{2\pi c} \Rightarrow k = \mu(2\pi c\nu)^2 \cong 575 \frac{N}{m}$$

where $T = 2\pi/\omega$ is the period of the system, $c = 2.998 \cdot 10^8 \frac{m}{s}$ is the speed of light, and $\nu = 440000 \text{ m}^{-1}$ (using the value from [6]). The densities of probability for $n = 0, 1, 2$ according to both the quantistic model and the classical model are plotted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Densities of probability for $n = 0, 1, 2$ according to both the quantistic model and the classical model of the diatomic hydrogen. These densities for one of the two atoms, assuming the other connected to the reference system.

CODE 2 (harmonic oscillations). This plots Figure 2.

```
# file name: Harmonic_Oscillator.py
#
# This script plots the probability density of one mass in a diatomic molecule modelled as
```

```

# two masses linked by a spring, using both the solution of the Schrodinger equation and
# the probability density derived through the harmonic stochastic process applied to the problem
# of the two masses linked by a spring as solved in classic mechanics. The numeric
# parameters are adapted to diatomic hydrogen.
#
import os # functions for interacting with the operating system
import pandas as pd # dataframes similar to R
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt # a plotting library
import math # mathematical functions
import numpy as np # arrays and matrices
from scipy.special import eval_hermite # for hermite polynomials
#
# Change the drectory, to the folder of the script
#
script_dir = os.path.dirname(os.path.abspath(__file__))
print(f"script_dir: {script_dir}")
os.chdir(script_dir)
#
# Constants
#
h = 6.6256e-34 # Planck constant (J*s)
#
# Parameters of the system
#
N = 3 # first n+1 Hermite Polynomials
r = 1000 # number of values for x in interval
m = 1.673e-27 # hydrogen mass (kg)
c = 2.998e8 # speed of light (m/s)
mu = m/2 # reduced mass
omega = math.sqrt(k/mu)
nu = 440000 # wavenumber (1/m)
#
# Function for classic oscillator amplitude
#
k = mu*(2*math.pi*c*nu)**2
#
# Function for classic oscillator amplitude
#
def An(n):
    amplitude = math.sqrt(h*(2*n+1)/(2*mu*omega*math.pi))
    return amplitude
#
# Function for quantistic wave function in x and n
#
def Psi(n,x):
    mul = math.sqrt(2*math.pi*m*omega/h)
    Hn = eval_hermite(n,x*mul)
    mul = math.sqrt(2*mu*omega/h)/((2**n)*math.factorial(n))
    mul = math.sqrt(mul)
    exp = math.exp(-(x**2)*math.pi*mu*omega/h)
    solution = mul*Hn*exp
    return solution
#
# Function for classic probability distribution in x and n
#
def CP(n,x):
    if x <= -An(n):
        probability = np.nan

```

```

elif x >= An(n):
    probability = np.nan
else:
    probability = 1/(math.pi*math.sqrt(An(n)**2 - x**2))
return probability
#
# Define abscissa
#
A_max = 1.1*An(N-1)
x_val = np.linspace(-A_max,A_max,r)
#
# Store in data frame the quantistic densities of probabilities
#
mydata = pd.DataFrame(0.0, index=range(r), columns=range(N))
for n in range(N):
    for i in range(r):
        x = x_val[i]
        mydata.at[i,n] = Psi(n,x)**2
mydata_Q = mydata
#
# Store in data frame the classic densities of probabilities
#
mydata = pd.DataFrame(0.0, index=range(r), columns=range(N))
for n in range(N):
    for i in range(r):
        x = x_val[i]
        mydata.at[i,n] = CP(n,x)
mydata_C = mydata
#
# Plot
#
colors = plt.rcParams['axes.prop_cycle'].by_key()['color'] # default matplotlib colors
x_plot = x_val * 1e10 # convert m → Å
#
plt.figure(figsize=(5,5))
for n in range(0,N):
    Y = mydata_Q[n]*1e-10 # m-1 → Å-1
    plt.plot(x_plot,Y,label=f'$f^q_{n}(x)$',linestyle='--',color=colors[n])
for n in range(0,N):
    Y = mydata_C[n]*1e-10 # m-1 → Å-1
    plt.plot(x_plot,Y,label=f'$f^c_{n}(x)$',linestyle='-',color=colors[n])
plt.xlabel('x (Å)')
plt.ylabel('$f_n(x)$ (Å-1)')
plt.title('Harmonic Oscillator ($H_2$)')
plt.legend()
plt.grid(True)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('Harmonic Oscillator.jpg', dpi=300)
plt.close() # Close the current figure

```

6 References

I used the material covered in chapter 7 of the Italian edition of [1] as a starting point, but I then decided to introduce Hermite's polynomials and functions of the second kind by direct solution of the Hermite equation, instead of using the Rodrigues' formula as definition. This makes my

presentation more similar to paragraph 18.9 of [2]. For the quantistic harmonic oscillator I considered both [1] and [3]. For the harmonic stochastic process, I used my notes [4], paragraph 8.1 in particular. In paragraph 9.2 of [5] it is possible to find the derivation of the equivalent system with a single mass for the harmonic oscillator with two masses. For the vibrational wavenumber I used the value reported by Majorana in his 100-year old notes [6] for equation 4.477.

1. Spiegel MR, "Fourier Analysis", McGraw-Hill, 1974
2. Riley KF, Hobson MP, Bence SJ, "Mathematical Methods for Physics and Engineering", Cambridge University Press, 3rd edition, 2006
3. Javorskij BM and Detlaf AA, "Manuale di Fisica", Edizioni Mir, Mosca, 1977
4. Maccallini, Paolo. "Variabili Aleatorie", 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20176250](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20176250)
5. Maccallini, Paolo. "Meccanica delle Vibrazioni", 2014. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20410124](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20410124)
6. "Ettore Majorana: Notes on Theoretical Physics", Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2003